

Teachers and learners teaching and learning: How does the use of participatory methods of research affect the design of an Augmented Reality app for the teaching of Mathematics

James O'Reilly

Mary Immaculate College

Once confined to the realms of science fiction, Augmented Reality (AR) is an emerging technology that has applications to industry, entertainment and communication. As the technology becomes increasingly accessible, potential applications of AR to education are coming to the fore. This research seeks to investigate how the technology can be applied to the Irish Primary Curriculum in its infancy, with the aim of suggesting how AR can be applied to the primary classroom moving forward. As part of this research, child participant researchers used a prototype AR app developed by an Irish primary school teacher, and suggested how the app could be improved over 8 weeks. The suggestions made by the children were then added to the app before they were asked to make further suggestions. This paper describes how the AR app developed over the course of the research relates to the Irish Primary Mathematics curriculum, to the Irish primary classroom and to the children who helped to improve it through discussion of the analysis of data collected in a Researcher Structured Diary, some of the changes made to the app, the worksheet given to the children and transcripts from Focus Group sessions.

Keywords: Mathematics, Augmented Reality, Participatory Methods, STEM, Primary Education

Introduction

Despite being an emerging technology Augmented Reality (AR), it is predicted, has the potential to have an impact on teaching and learning in the future (Ibáñez & Delgado-Kloos, 2018). In recent years this technology has become increasingly accessible, particularly with the development of increasingly powerful handheld devices that can support a variety of AR applications. This research aims to consider AR for Irish primary education from its foundation, with the intention of suggesting how the technology may be effectively used in primary classrooms for the teaching of Mathematics and the development of 3D spatial awareness and pattern recognition. The AR app being used in this research, provisionally called PopCubes, was a piece of software which had been designed by an experienced Irish primary school teacher with consideration of the current Irish Primary Mathematics curriculum (NCCA, 1999). That the prototype software being investigated was designed solely by an Irish primary school teacher who does not have a background in software design is one novel aspect of this research. Adding to the novelty, this research adopted participatory methods. These participatory methods allowed child participant researchers to contribute to the design of PopCubes over a number of weeks, directly influencing and determining how the app changed and developed over time. This paper will consider how the use of PopCubes relates to Mathematics specifically, and the potential that the child participant researchers, and the teacher researcher, see for the use of AR in the teaching of Mathematics.

Software Used

Before beginning an 8-week intervention with the children the decision was made to design and build an AR app, which resulted in the creation of PopCubes. This decision was made after an investigation into the AR apps available, none of which met the criteria of this research. The criteria being considered included age appropriateness, direct links to the Irish Mathematics curriculum and the exclusion of potential for engagement with individuals outside the school through the technology. Before beginning the development of PopCubes the researcher developed an App Design Tool which considered the Irish Primary Curriculum (NCCA, 1999), educational theory (Freire, 1972; Karl, 2012; Papert, 1980; Sadovnik, 1991), good pedagogical practice and Irish educational policy (DES, 2017; DES, 2015). PopCubes was developed, on and off, over the course of approximately a year. 2D assets for PopCubes were created using Microsoft Paint while 3D assets were built in Tinkercad, a free, web-based tool for 3D Computer Aided Design (CAD). PopCubes was developed using Unity, a free piece of software that can be used for the development of video games and apps.

One area of the Irish Primary Curriculum emphasised in PopCubes is the Strand of Shape and Space (NCCA 1999.) As they explored scenes in PopCubes the children were asked to complete a worksheet which asked them to explore aspects of Shape and Space and to use their understanding of the area to propose their own additions to the scenes.

When using PopCubes users point the camera of their device at a card cube, upon which a virtual 3D augmentation, referred to in this paper as a scene, appears. Figure 1 shows a photo of one of the card cubes alongside the cube as it appears in PopCubes. The user has access to three buttons, each of which serve a different purpose. The Enlarge button allows users to enlarge parts of the scene to take a closer look, the Pen button allows users to annotate what they can see on the screen and the Camera tool allows users to take a screenshot of what is on the screen at the time of the button being pressed.

Figure 1

Two cubes with and without their virtual augmentation

Methods

Before engaging in any research activities, ethical clearance was sought, and obtained, from the Mary Immaculate College Ethics Committee. Consent for the carrying out of the research was sought from the school principal and the class teacher before parental consent,

after which assent was obtained from the children. Of the 22 children in the class, one child elected not to take part.

This research adopted qualitative methods with aspects of quantitative data collection. Much data was collected over the course of the intervention, some of which is beyond the scope of this paper. Each week children used the prototype software and gave feedback on how it could be improved by adding, changing or removing something. The children's suggestions were then implemented into the app before they used it again, after which they gave further feedback to be implemented. This piece will focus on data collected from the Focus Groups and Structured Researcher Diary, both of which were analysed through their transcription and coding (Braun & Clarke, 2008) after the intervention. Focus Groups were selected as they can allow for the collection of living, dynamic data (Hennink et al., 2012) and the Structured Researcher Diary was used to allow for the recording of reactions, hypotheses and difficulties encountered (Miles & Huberman, 1994). While many findings emerged over the course of the research, this paper will consider some findings that relate to the primary Mathematics curriculum (NCCA, 1999).

Findings

As the research began it became apparent that the children enjoyed using PopCubes. As the children used the app, they expressed positive affirmations of it saying "I like everything in it" (Pupil 2, Week 5) or that they "love" seeing their suggestions integrated into it (Pupil 21, Week 2). The children enjoyed exploring the scenes that appeared when they focused their camera on the cubes, telling others that they "like finding Robbie the Robot" (Pupil 5, Week 1), a robot hidden in each of the scenes, and even suggested that I make "finding stuff in the map a little harder" (Pupil 14, Week 3). Not all feedback was praise, however, with children saying "I don't really like it" (Pupil 21, Week 2) and that they thought the scenes did not look good "because it's all cubes" (Pupil 19, Week 8). Aspects of PopCubes had the potential to be distracting, as recorded in the Researcher Structured Diary (Week 1, Group 4; Week 6, Group 2).

The children did recognise some of the potential for learning through PopCubes. When asked if a child could learn from the app children responded "Yes. They could completely learn" (Pupil 13, Week 2). Children described engaging with the Primary Mathematics Curriculum describing "spheres" (Pupil 8, Week 2), discussing verticality (Pupil 12, Week 7) and saying that, through the app, users "could learn their shapes" (Pupil 16, Week 3). The researcher recorded that children were using "Maths language to ask one another questions" (Week 1, Group 2). The researcher recorded that children were using "positional" (Week 5, Group 4) and "directional" (Week 7, Group 4) language when describing aspects of the scenes. The children enjoyed a challenge (Pupil 5, Week 1) and children also made suggestions about the worksheet, suggesting questions such as "how many cubes can you find? How many spheres?" (Pupil 10, Week 1). From an early stage the researcher noted that engagement with Mathematics was strong when "working on sheets" (Week 2, Group 3). As the research progressed pupils suggested adding levels to the worksheet, adding a system of keys and locks which meant users could progress to the next

level when they had completed a certain number of questions, a change which the researcher noted was exciting for the children (Week 3, Group 4).

Children seemed to enjoy taking part in the Mathematical aspects of PopCubes. On the worksheet children were asked to find 2D and 3D shapes hidden throughout the scene and children enjoyed exploring the scene and looking for shapes, saying “I love looking for shapes” (Pupil 8, Week 2) and “I love 3D shapes” (Pupil 16, Week 8).

This was reflected in the Researcher Diary, where it was recorded that children were “enthusiastic users of worksheets” (Week 4, Group 1). The 2D shapes were an addition to the scenes, a change made by the researcher after Week 2 because children were finding it difficult to identify faces of 3D shapes as 2D shapes, resulting in them being unable to complete the worksheet. This addition allowed for closer links to the 2D shape aspect of Shape and Space, as recorded in the Structured Diary (Week 3, Group 2). Towards the end of the intervention the children described finding the worksheet easy, in particular finding the 2D shapes. The finding of 3D shapes was described as “more difficult” but still “easy” (Pupil 6, Week 8).

References

- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2008). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Department of Education and Science (2015). *Digital strategy for schools 2015-2020*. Dublin: Department of Education and Science
- Department of Education and Skills, (2017). *STEM Education Consultation Report 2017*. Dublin: Department of Education and Skills
- Freire, P. (1972). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. London: Penguin Books
- Hennink, M., Hutter, I., Bailey, A. (2012). *Qualitative research methods*. London: Sage
- Ibáñez, M.B., Delgado-Kloos, C. (2018). Augmented reality for STEM learning: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 123, 109-123.
- Karl, M. (2012). *The gamification of learning and instruction: Game-based methods and strategies for training and education*. San Francisco: Pfeiffer Wiley
- Miles, M., Huberman, A. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis*. London: Sage
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (1999). *Mathematics primary school curriculum*. Dublin: National Council for Curriculum and Assessment
- Papert, S. (1980). *Mindstorms: Children, computers and powerful ideas*. Great Britain: The Harvester Press Limited.
- Sadovnik, A.R (1991). ‘Basil Bernstein's Theory of Pedagogic Practice: A Structuralist Approach. *Sociology of Education*, 64(1), 48-63.